

Archbishop, Beggar, or Intermediary? Rethinking Nathanael of Leukas in Seventeenth-Century Europe

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Abstract

This article re-examines the figure of Nathanael, Archbishop of Leukas, whose presence in Western Europe between the 1640s and 1660s has traditionally been interpreted as that of an itinerant alms-seeking cleric. Drawing on archival traces from Zurich, Rostock, Bremen, Venice, and Paris, the study reconstructs a more complex trajectory involving sustained engagement with Protestant and Catholic networks. The article proposes that Nathanael may be understood as a flexible intermediary between confessional worlds.

Introduction

The figure of Nathanael, Archbishop of Leukas (Santa Maura), who appears in Western European sources from the 1640s until the early 1660s, has generally been interpreted within the conventional framework of early modern Greek mobility as that of an itinerant Orthodox cleric seeking financial assistance¹. Modern scholarship often classifies such individuals among the numerous Greek ecclesiastics who travelled to Western Europe in order to collect alms, typically for the ransom of captives or the support of ecclesiastical institutions under Ottoman rule.

Yet the surviving evidence concerning Nathanael resists this conventional interpretation.

Unlike the majority of Greek petitioners², Nathanael was not a marginal cleric but a serving archbishop of the Orthodox Church, who had occupied the see of Leukas for approximately sixteen years before withdrawing from his post around 1640. His subsequent activity in Western Europe presents a pattern that diverges markedly from that of typical alms-seekers.

Rather than limiting himself to fundraising, Nathanael engaged with major centers of theological and intellectual exchange across confessional boundaries. His presence is attested in Reformed circles, notably in Zurich, where he entered into doctrinal discussions and received theological questionnaires concerning key points of dispute between Christian confessions. At the same time, his later appearance in Catholic contexts—particularly in Venice, where he is described as a “Greek Catholic” (*catolique grec*)—suggests not a fixed confessional alignment but an ability, or willingness, to operate across competing religious spheres.

Further evidence points to Nathanael’s integration into scholarly and intellectual networks. Together with a companion identified as Andreas Palaiologos of Thessaloniki, he was registered at the University of Rostock under circumstances that

¹ See Saracino S., *Griechen im Heiligen Römischen Reich*, 2024, p. 39.

² On mobility and Greek clerics, see Molly Greene, *The Edinburgh History of the Greeks*, 2015

imply facilitated or honorary admission rather than ordinary student enrollment. The independent presence of Andreas in other learned contexts, including his association with circles linked to the theologian Johannes Cocceius, reinforces the impression that Nathanael's travels were not solitary but involved a small, functionally coherent partnership capable of linguistic mediation and intellectual exchange.

Equally striking is the instability of Nathanael's recorded surname in Western sources, where he appears under different forms, including Masarinos and Diassarinos. This variation raises important questions regarding identity construction, self-representation, and the strategic adaptation of personal data in diverse confessional and political environments.

Taken together, these elements invite a reassessment of Nathanael's role and activity. Rather than viewing him solely as an itinerant petitioner, this study explores the hypothesis that he functioned as an intermediary operating between the Orthodox East and the confessional worlds of Western Europe, engaging in a form of informal or semi-structured religious diplomacy during a period marked by intense theological and political conflict in the aftermath of the Thirty Years' War.

While no explicit documentary evidence has yet been identified to confirm a formal mandate from the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople, the patterns of movement, association, and activity exhibited by Nathanael suggest a degree of intentionality and strategic positioning that cannot be adequately explained within the traditional model of alms-seeking mobility.

This study aims to reconstruct Nathanael's trajectory and reassess his historical significance by situating him within the broader context of early modern confessional interaction, intellectual exchange, and trans-imperial mobility.

Vienna and the Threshold of Departure (1638–1640)

over several The first indication that Nathanael's later activity in Western Europe may not have been incidental is his reported presence in Vienna in 1638. This episode, though still insufficiently documented, deserves particular attention, as it places the Orthodox archbishop in one of the most significant political and confessional centers of seventeenth-century Europe at a critical historical moment.

In 1638, Vienna stood at the heart of Habsburg power and functioned as a major stronghold of Catholic influence during the later phases of the Thirty Years' War. Any appearance there by an Orthodox prelate from Ottoman-controlled territory would have been highly unusual and, at the very least, indicative of access to networks extending beyond the boundaries of the Ottoman world.

This early western contact predates Nathanael's formal withdrawal from his archiepiscopal seat in Leukas around 1640 and suggests that his engagement with Western Europe may have begun prior to his supposed retirement. Rather than marking a clear break between an "active episcopal career" and a later "itinerant phase," the available evidence points instead to a **transitional period in which exploratory contacts were already being established.**

Such a reading invites a reconsideration of the circumstances surrounding his departure from Leukas. Officially, Nathanael appears to have withdrawn from his see without immediate formal replacement and to have relocated to the Ionian Islands, most likely Zakynthos, where he is said to have entered a monastic setting. However, the absence of clear evidence for sustained monastic activity, combined with his subsequent rapid integration into Western intellectual and confessional networks, raises doubts as to whether this withdrawal should be understood as a purely religious retirement.

Instead, it is possible to interpret this phase as part of a **deliberate repositioning outside Ottoman jurisdiction**, facilitating freer movement and communication with Western actors. The Ionian Islands, situated at the intersection of Ottoman and Venetian spheres, offered precisely such a liminal space, allowing individuals to operate with a degree of flexibility unavailable within the empire.

Within this framework, Nathanael's presence in Vienna in 1638 may be understood not as an isolated episode, but as an **initial point of contact or reconnaissance**, preceding a more sustained engagement with Western Europe after 1640. His departure from Leukas would thus mark not the end of his public activity, but the beginning of a new and less transparent phase.

The absence of explicit documentation regarding the motives, sponsors, or institutional backing of this transition remains a major obstacle. Nevertheless, the convergence of chronological and geographical indicators suggests that Nathanael's movement toward Western Europe was not sudden or accidental, but rather the result of a process unfolding years.

This interpretation gains further plausibility when viewed in light of his later trajectory, which demonstrates not only mobility, but also sustained access to confessional elites and scholarly institutions across Europe.

The “Silent Years”: Withdrawal, Mobility, and Possible Preparation (1640–1646)

Following his withdrawal from the archiepiscopal seat of Leukas around 1640, Nathanael enters a period for which direct documentation remains scarce. According to later accounts, he relocated to Zakynthos and adopted a monastic life³, possibly in a dependency associated with a local monastery. This phase has traditionally been interpreted as one of retirement and withdrawal from active ecclesiastical and political engagement.

However, such an interpretation raises a number of difficulties.

Firstly, there is little concrete evidence to support the notion of sustained monastic activity. Secondly, Nathanael's subsequent rapid and effective integration into Western European theological and intellectual networks suggests a level of preparation, orientation, and connection that would be difficult to reconcile with a prolonged period of isolation.

³ See Moussouraç D.I.(2003)

These considerations invite a reassessment of the years between 1640 and 1646, not as a phase of inactivity, but as a period of transition and possible preparation.

The geographical position of Zakynthos, lying outside direct Ottoman control while remaining closely connected to the Greek ecclesiastical world, made it a particularly suitable environment for such a transitional phase. It offered both a plausible public narrative—withdrawal into monastic life—and a degree of practical flexibility for travel and communication.

Within this framework, it is conceivable that Nathanael's movements during these years were not limited to Zakynthos. Although no direct documentation has yet been identified, the possibility of intermittent travel to Constantinople cannot be excluded, especially in light of the need for coordination, authorization, or at least tacit approval for the type of activities he would later undertake in Western Europe.

A further element that deserves consideration is the broader ecclesiastical context of the period, particularly the shifting orientations of the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople. The mid-seventeenth century was marked by significant fluctuations in the Patriarchate's engagement with Western confessional groups, reflecting both internal theological debates and external political pressures.

In this regard, the patriarchates of Parthenius II of Constantinople⁴ have been associated in modern scholarship with differing confessional tendencies, at times more receptive to Protestant contacts and at others more aligned with Catholic interlocutors. While direct evidence linking Nathanael to these policy shifts remains lacking, the chronological proximity between these developments and the later trajectory of his travels is noteworthy.

Indeed, Nathanael's subsequent movement from Reformed environments in the late 1640s to Catholic contexts in the early 1650s may be seen as broadly consistent with a pattern of adaptive engagement across confessional boundaries, rather than adherence to a single theological alignment.

Whether this reflects personal strategy, external influence, or a more structured form of coordination remains an open question. Nevertheless, the convergence of these elements suggests that the years 1640–1646 should not be regarded as a historical void, but rather as a crucial, though still opaque, phase in the formation of Nathanael's later activity in Western Europe.

Nathanael in Reformed Europe: Networks, Theology, and Mobility (1647–1649)

By the mid-1640s, Nathanael emerges clearly within the documentary record of Western Europe, no longer as a shadowy or transitional figure, but as an active participant in trans-confessional exchanges⁵. His presence is attested in several centers associated with the Reformed world, most notably Zurich, Bremen, and Rostock.

⁴ See Gedeon M. (1885)

⁵ See Goar J. (1647)

In Zurich, Nathanael came into contact with leading representatives of the Reformed Church. A particularly revealing document is a letter addressed to him by the theologian Johann Caspar Schweizer⁶, written in Greek. The letter contains a structured theological questionnaire addressing central issues of confessional divergence, including the nature of the Eucharist, the status of apocryphal books, baptismal practice, fasting regulations, and ecclesiastical hierarchy.

The formulation of these questions closely parallels similar inquiries circulated among Eastern patriarchates earlier in the century, suggesting that Nathanael was not treated as an isolated individual, but rather as a representative of the Eastern Church whose responses could carry broader doctrinal significance. His role in this exchange thus appears to extend beyond that of a passive recipient of Western theological curiosity, positioning him instead as an interlocutor within an ongoing process of confessional negotiation.

At the same time, Nathanael's integration into scholarly networks is further illustrated by his association with the German Reformed theologian Johannes Cocceius. His companion, Andreas Palaiologos of Thessaloniki, is known to have signed Cocceius' *album amicorum* in Bremen, a practice typically reserved for individuals participating in learned and intellectual circles. This evidence confirms that the two men operated within environments that combined theological discourse with academic sociability.

Perhaps the most striking documentary trace of Nathanael's presence in Protestant Europe is his registration at the University of Rostock⁷. In the matriculation records, dated to March 1648, he appears under the name Nathanael Masarinos ex insula Chionatus, archiepiscopus Leucados in Graecia, accompanied by Andreas Paleologus Thessalonicensis Graecus. The explicit identification of Nathanael as a serving archbishop, combined with the formal structure of the entry, suggests that his registration was not that of an ordinary student, but rather a symbolic or facilitated inclusion reflecting his status and connections.

This record is of particular importance for two reasons. First, it provides a contemporaneous attestation of Nathanael's presence in Northern Europe at a precise date. Second, the use of the surname Masarinos—distinct from the later Diassorinos—raises important questions regarding identity and self-representation, especially in light of the consistency with which the title of archbishop is maintained across contexts.

Taken together, these elements reveal a pattern of activity that is difficult to reconcile with the traditional model of itinerant alms-seeking. Nathanael does not appear as a marginal figure moving opportunistically between locations, but rather as an individual who gains access to key nodes of Reformed intellectual life, engages in structured theological dialogue, and is received in academic institutions with a degree of recognition.

Moreover, his movement across geographically distant centers—Zurich, Bremen, Rostock—within a relatively short period suggests not only mobility, but also the

⁶ See Henny S. (2020): p. 450

⁷ See Hofmeister A. (1895)

existence of networks facilitating his passage and reception. Whether these networks were primarily confessional, scholarly, or diplomatic in nature remains an open question; however, their effectiveness is evident in the consistency and depth of his engagements.

This phase of Nathanael's journey thus represents the first clearly documented stage of his interaction with Western Europe. It establishes him as a participant in Protestant intellectual and theological exchanges, while at the same time laying the groundwork for the subsequent shift in his trajectory toward Catholic environments in the following decade.

From Reformed Dialogue to Catholic Engagement: Nathanael in the 1650s

By the early 1650s, the trajectory of Nathanael's activity in Western Europe appears to undergo a significant shift. While his presence in the late 1640s is clearly embedded within Reformed and Protestant networks, subsequent evidence places him within Catholic environments, suggesting a reorientation—whether strategic, circumstantial, or externally influenced—of his engagements⁸.

A key document attesting to this transition is the report of the French ambassador in Venice, dated to 1652, which refers to him as:

*“Nathanael Diassorino, archbishop of Santa Maura of Leucade, Greek Catholic (catolique grec), persecuted by the infidels.”*⁹

This description is striking for several reasons.

First, the designation “*Greek Catholic*” does not necessarily imply formal conversion to Roman Catholicism, but rather situates Nathanael within a flexible interpretive space, where Eastern clerics could be presented as potential allies or interlocutors in the broader Catholic effort to engage with the Orthodox world. Such terminology was often used strategically in diplomatic and ecclesiastical contexts, particularly within the framework of Catholic missionary initiatives linked to institutions such as the Congregation for the Propagation of the Faith (*Propaganda Fide*).

Second, the narrative of persecution—“persecuted by the infidels”—aligns with a well-established rhetorical pattern employed by Eastern clerics seeking support in Western Europe. However, in Nathanael's case, this claim appears difficult to reconcile with the known historical context of his episcopacy in Leukas, where no concrete evidence of such persecution or of involvement in anti-Ottoman activity during his tenure (1624–1640) has been identified.

This discrepancy raises the possibility that such representations were **contextually constructed**, tailored to resonate with the expectations and priorities of specific audiences. In other words, Nathanael's public profile may have been **adapted according to the confessional and political environment in which he operated**.

⁸ Le Quien M. (1740): p.154

⁹ See Poncet O. (2022): p.453

Further reinforcing this impression is the shift in the recorded form of his surname—from *Masarinos* in the Protestant context of the late 1640s to *Diassorinos* in Catholic documentation of the early 1650s. This change cannot easily be explained as a simple transcriptional variation and instead suggests a more deliberate reconfiguration of identity, possibly linked to differing strategies of presentation or to the use of alternative personal or familial designations.

During this phase, Nathanael's activity appears increasingly oriented toward major Catholic centers, culminating in his presence in Paris, where he is reported to have died in 1661 while attending a Catholic ceremony¹⁰. His prolonged stay in France, combined with continued efforts to secure financial and institutional support, indicates sustained engagement with Catholic networks at the highest level.

Importantly, this Catholic phase does not erase or contradict his earlier involvement with Protestant circles. Rather, it suggests a pattern of **sequential or parallel engagement across confessional boundaries**, reinforcing the view that Nathanael operated with a degree of flexibility that exceeds the expectations typically associated with itinerant Orthodox clergy of the period.

This transition may also be considered in relation to broader developments within the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople, where shifting policies toward Western confessions have been observed during the mid-seventeenth century. While no direct causal link can be established, the alignment between Nathanael's changing sphere of activity and these broader ecclesiastical dynamics remains suggestive.

In sum, Nathanael's movement into Catholic environments during the 1650s represents not a rupture, but an extension of his earlier trajectory—one that highlights his capacity to navigate the complex and often competing confessional landscapes of early modern Europe.

Rethinking Nathanael of Leukas: Mobility, Identity, and Purpose

The case of Nathanael, archbishop of Leukas, presents a striking example of the complexities inherent in the study of early modern Greek ecclesiastical figures operating within a trans-imperial and trans-confessional environment. Traditionally portrayed as an itinerant cleric seeking financial assistance in Western Europe, Nathanael's trajectory, when examined in light of the available evidence, invites a more nuanced interpretation.

The reconstruction of his movements—from his departure from Leukas around 1640, through his documented presence in Reformed centers such as Zurich and Rostock in the late 1640s, to his later activity within Catholic contexts in Venice and Paris—reveals a pattern of sustained engagement with major confessional and intellectual networks across Europe.

This pattern is difficult to reconcile with the conventional model of the *mendicant prelate*. Instead, Nathanael appears as a figure capable of navigating multiple and often competing environments, adapting his presentation and affiliations according to

¹⁰ See Henny S. (2020)

context. His participation in structured theological exchanges, his access to academic institutions such as the University of Rostock, and his reception by both Protestant and Catholic interlocutors point toward a level of agency and recognition that exceeds that of a marginal or purely opportunistic actor.

Particularly significant is the fluidity of his recorded identity. The variation between the surnames *Masarinos* and *Diassorinos*, alongside the consistent retention of his episcopal title, suggests not confusion but **controlled adaptability**. Such flexibility may reflect the practical realities of cross-cultural movement, but it may also indicate a deliberate strategy of self-representation shaped by the expectations of different audiences.

Equally noteworthy is the chronological structure of his activity. The so-called “silent years” (1640–1646), far from constituting a period of inactivity, emerge as a plausible phase of transition and preparation. When considered alongside the shifting confessional orientations of the Ecumenical Patriarchate of Constantinople, particularly under figures such as Parthenius II of Constantinople, Nathanael’s subsequent movement between Protestant and Catholic spheres acquires additional interpretive depth. While no direct evidence confirms institutional coordination, the alignment between his trajectory and broader ecclesiastical dynamics remains suggestive.

On this basis, it becomes possible—though not demonstrable in a strict documentary sense—to advance the hypothesis that Nathanael’s activity in Western Europe may have served purposes extending beyond personal survival or individual advancement. His sustained and structured engagement with multiple confessional centers raises the question of whether he functioned, at least in part, as an intermediary or observer within a wider process of interaction between the Orthodox East and the confessionalized West.

Such an interpretation does not require the assumption of a formally documented or centrally organized “mission.” Rather, it allows for the possibility of **informal, adaptive, and context-dependent roles**, shaped by a combination of personal initiative, ecclesiastical background, and the opportunities afforded by a rapidly changing European landscape.

In this light, Nathanael should perhaps be understood not as an anomaly, but as a representative—albeit an unusually well-documented one—of a broader category of mobile Orthodox clerics who operated at the intersection of diplomacy, theology, and intellectual exchange during the seventeenth century.

The limitations of the available evidence remain significant, and many aspects of his life—particularly his origins, the nature of his affiliations, and the precise motivations behind his travels—continue to resist definitive explanation. Nevertheless, the convergence of documentary traces, contextual indicators, and patterns of behavior justifies a reconsideration of his role.

Future research, particularly in archival collections associated with institutions such as the Congregation for the Propagation of the Faith, as well as in lesser-explored university and diplomatic archives, may yet provide further clarity. Until then,

Nathanael's career remains best approached not through reductive categorization, but through an appreciation of its ambiguity—an ambiguity that reflects the broader complexities of early modern Mediterranean and European history.

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